

MIMESIS, PRECEDENT, AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A CONVERSATION WITH MARIO CARPO

ANDREJA PROKOPIJEVIĆ: Early digital theorists often suggested that architects would gradually move from designing objects to designing processes, rules, and systems. Today, design increasingly unfolds through computational systems capable of generating spatial proposals from large bodies of precedents and data. Where would you situate these developments within the longer shift you have described, from the authorial model of design towards more distributed or statistical forms of authorship?

MARIO CARPO: The short answer is that we should look at the history of computation in its entire duration, from when it started to this day, to see how the different parameters we introduced were ebbing and flowing over time. So, when it all started in 1956, when the idea of artificial intelligence was invented, the first methodologies of AI—which came by Marvin Minsky in 1960–61—defined artificial intelligence as a general problem-solving machine. It’s a thinking machine. They called such machines electronic brains.

This first age of artificial intelligence boomed in the 1960s and was still influential in the 1970s when architects started to experiment with it—think of Nicholas Negroponte and a bit earlier Cedric Price—this was the idea of artificial intelligence as a thinking machine, which for architects is a machine that does design, makes design choices, which was Negroponte’s idea in *The Architectural Machine*. This machine replaces the architect. It makes design choices. The idea was: with a bigger computer, more computing power, we will make it work. But as we know, in the 1970s, it didn’t work. This dream of the 1960s and 1970s was abandoned. In the history of computer science, this is called the winter of artificial intelligence, when many came to the conclusion that not only it did not work, but that the conceptual framework was wrong from the start. They concluded it would never work. So, this story starts in the

1950s, booms in the 1960s, declines in the 1970s, disappears in the 1980s. Now, when we come to what I call the digital turn in architecture, a story which starts in the early 1990s with Peter Eisenman, Greg Lynn, Bernard Cache, etc., the computer we used at that time was not a thinking machine, but a drawing machine. It did not make design choices. It was a tool that makes drawings—spline modelling, etc.—what later became parametricism. But it was not a thinking machine.

So, phase one: computers are thinking machines—extinguished in the 1970s–80s. In the 1990s: computers are drawing machines. And this was computation in architecture until 10 years ago, when artificial intelligence came back. But the second coming of artificial intelligence—machine learning—is what made it work. And unlike in the 1960s, this time it works. Today we are back to where we started 60 years ago: dealing with intelligent machines that can make design choices. But this is a novelty, because everything we knew as the digital turn was not about artificial intelligence, it was about the automation of drawing. Now we are back to artificial intelligence as such: a thinking machine, an intelligent machine, a machine to which we can delegate design choices. It is brand new. We don't know how to deal with it. We don't know how it will affect design agency. Because before, we were still in charge. Now it's a new story. And I don't know where it came from and I have no idea where it's going. We'll see.

AP: As generative AI produces new forms through the recombination and transformation of existing precedents, parallels have often been drawn with the logic of Mannerism. You describe Mannerism not simply as a continuation of tradition but as a critical engagement with it. How might this notion of “licensed deviation,” as you once noted, help us understand contemporary algorithmic design practices?

MC: The way I define it, generative AI is an imitation machine. The term is controversial because we do not all mean the same thing by imitation. But at any rate, an imitation machine is a machine that generates new images which are similar to the images on which it was trained. Generative AI is a machine that makes new stuff out of old stuff. Think of it as a grinder, like a food processor. What you put in determines what you take out. If you train the model with a dataset made exclusively of white dogs with a black nose, what you get out is going to be white dogs with a black nose. If you train the machine with a dataset made of yellow cats with a pink nose, you will get yellow cats with a pink nose. It is similarity.

It is about style transfer, or what I call the imitation machine—the automation of visual imitation.

We shall come back to that, because imitation is not a neutral term. It is in fact a very problematic one. But if you want to go into the mannerism discussion, there is an article I wrote in *Log* a couple of years ago where I discussed this topic with regard to Peter Eisenman and mannerism. The idea that mannerism critiques precedent is similar, to some extent, to what generative AI is doing, because generative AI transforms precedent. But there is a difference, to which Peter Eisenman is very much alert. When a human being—someone like him, or any mannerist in time—refers to precedent, you recycle precedent, you critique it, you take a position. You take a stance *vis-à-vis* precedent: you may like it, you may not like it, or you may only like it to a certain extent.

Mannerism is, let's put it that way, calculated rule-breaking, or regulated rule-breaking, as in the Saussurean dialectic of *langue* and *parole* in structural linguistics. There is a code, you learn the rules of the code, and then you break some, because that is how languages work. Now, generative AI appears to be doing something like that. But one thing that generative AI cannot do is take a critical position *vis-à-vis* precedent, because it does not have a critical position. Generative AI cannot do calculated rule-breaking because it is not a rule-based system. It does not know rules, does not use rules, does not make rules, and does not break rules. So, there is one thing that generative AI cannot be: it cannot be mannerist. Because in order to be mannerist, you must know what the rules are and which rules you want to break. Generative AI imitates, but imitates in a way that a child does before going to school, without knowing the rules. We only learn the rules when we go to school. We learn grammar, we learn to write. As a kid, before going to school, one can speak by imitating voices, pure imitation, without knowing any rules. The rules we learn later. Then, once we know the rules, we may break them—because we know them, or because we choose to ignore them. But that happens after learning.

Generative AI is in the state of a child before going to school. It imitates, but it does not know the rules. So, it can imitate mannerist works. It can be mannerist in style, but it cannot be mannerist in spirit. Because a mannerist in spirit is someone who knows the rule he is breaking. And generative AI cannot do that—not today, and probably not in the near future, although who knows? Things change fast. But for the time being, generative AI cannot break rules because it cannot make rules. It does not work with rules. There are no rules in generative AI.

We had rules in earlier computational systems—shape grammars, for example—but this is something we have abandoned. Generative AI does not work with rules. So, there cannot be any form of mannerism as a critical stance, as a critique of precedent. Generative AI can imitate precedent in the way a child would before going to school. So, it is very good at learning, but it does not know grammar. That is both the advantage and the disadvantage of generative AI. It is at the mental age of a child of about five years, before entering school. That is where it stands. It may improve over time, but for the time being, it does not.

AP: If we now have forms that are generated through a logic of precedent and variation, it affects the way we perceive them as images. Mechanical printing once created a new kind of visual trust by guaranteeing the identical reproducibility of images. In contrast, today's digital images, especially those generated by AI, can be perfectly realistic yet entirely synthetic. Do you think contemporary visual culture is entering a new phase in which the authority of images is once again becoming unstable?

MC: Yes, that is happening, but this is not new. This is more of the same. It all started with the rise of digital images in the 1980s or early 1990s. The idea of pixelated images—images made of pixels—has all been explained in a fantastic book by William Mitchell, *The Reconfigured Eye*, published in the early 1990s. At the time nobody had a digital camera, but he already knew how it worked. All the explanation is there. In a nutshell, the images we knew—photographic images—are an indexical trace of reality because they are materially created by the impact of electrons inside the camera. So, you have a traditional camera, not a digital one. It is a box with a lens and a photosensitive film. You take a snapshot, and what actually happens is a mechanical operation: light goes through the lens, it is inverted because it is a camera obscura, and particles hit the photographic film. When they hit, they leave an imprint. That is what we call an indexical trace. If something is recorded on that film, it is because something physically happened. That is why such images could function as evidence. They could be used in court. They recorded something that actually took place—unless someone was cheating. Of course, manipulation always existed. For example, in the Soviet Union, when someone in the Politburo fell out of favour, they would reprint photographs and remove that person. But that required manual, chemical manipulation, and often you could detect it. So, the indexical image had the value of proof.

If the film inside the camera records the imprint of a picture where you see that there was someone behind you when that picture was taken, it means that person was there. The image records an event that happened.

Then digital cameras came. Inside the camera there is no film, but a raster of photosensitive sensors. They convert incoming light into numerical data. So, the image becomes a number. Once it is a mathematical notation, the indexical link between image and reality is broken. The event is translated into a sequence of numbers. And once it is a number, anything can be modified. For example, digital cameras automatically remove red-eye. But that is not a recording of what happened; it is an algorithmic manipulation. William Mitchell already pointed this out in the early 1990s. He said that previously, if a newspaper received a photograph, they assumed that the event had occurred. But with digital imaging, that assumption could no longer be taken for granted. The indexical relation was already broken at that time—30 or 40 years ago.

Today it is entirely broken. What we are experiencing now is not a completely new phenomenon, but an intensification of a process that started decades ago. The idea that images are reliable traces of reality has already been fundamentally undermined.

ŽELJKO RADINKOVIĆ: What do you mean by parametric spaces of possibility? If one assumes that parameters can generate infinitely many variants, does this not risk losing specifically human or existential possibility in favour of a kind of indifferent arbitrariness? Can we therefore still meaningfully speak of so-called mass individualisation?

MC: Mass customisation is the term that I use. Mass individualisation means the same. Yes, everything that is digital is, by definition, mass customisable. It does not mean that it is customised, but in principle it can be. Everything that is parametric is, by definition, mass customisable. Like the parametric notation we studied in high school in calculus: you write the equation of a parabola with x and y , and then parameters a , b , and c . That is not the notation of a single parabola; it is the notation of a family of parabolas. All different, all similar. You change the values of the parameters and you get different parabolas—larger, smaller, wider—but they are all parabolas because the x - y notation is in the same format.

The principle of parametricism, which is the core principle of all digital notation, is that you never notate an object; you notate a family of objects. This is what Bernard Cache, inspired by Gilles Deleuze, called

the objectile—not the object, but a generic object. You notate a family of objects, not an individual one. Then, once you have the family, you assign values to the parameters and you individualise it. You obtain a specific instance. In Aristotelian terms, you notate a genus, within which you have species. Or in mathematical terms, a set. So, the marketing term is customisation; the philosophical term is individuation. That is how digital fabrication works.

This idea is not entirely new. In scholastic philosophy, there was no science of the individual, only a science of species or genera. It is an old idea, but parametricism and digitality have translated it into the way we fabricate objects, not just how we conceptualise them.

ŽR: Would you describe your understanding of architecture as a step toward post-human design logic?

MC: Post-human? I would say pre-humanist. If I were an Aristotelian philosopher in the 14th century, I would describe the world in these terms. I would not have the machine to implement it, of course. So, I would not say post-human. I would say pre-mechanical. The idea of the human we have in mind is the human of the industrial age. We are getting out of that. We are moving away from the human subject of the industrial, mechanical environment—the world of identical reproduction, Benjamin’s aura, etc. The idea of endless variability in digital tools is closer to the variability of artisanal craft before industrial standardization. In the artisanal world, everything is different. In the digital world, everything can be different again—unless we deliberately choose to make identical copies. Industrial production made us accustomed to sameness. But that was an exception, in historical terms.

ŽR: How would you situate your conception of architecture in relation to Walter Benjamin? In Benjamin’s analysis, when infinitely many copies exist, the original loses its privileged status, its aura. In parametric design, there is often no original in the traditional sense, yet a series of individual forms emerges. Do you see these individuations as carriers of a new kind of auratic determination?

MC: Walter Benjamin was absolutely right in conceptualising the technical logic of a machine-made environment. If we live in a world of machine-made objects—think of printing—you have one matrix, one

mould, and you produce identical copies. The original has an aura; the copies do not. This logic extends into industrial production. The original design belongs to the author, and each identical reproduction generates royalties. That is the logic of industrial modernity. But this logic does not apply to craft, and it does not apply to digital making. In craft, every object is different. An artisan makes each object individually, adapting to materials, circumstances, or even personal preference. Digital making works in a similar way. The digital maker is today's artisan. The concept of aura does not apply in the same way. We only need identical reproduction in certain cases—for example, a ballpoint pen. The one I'm holding right now is good for all. Anyone can use it. But in other cases, such as, say, dental crowns, variation is necessary because each tooth is different. Today we have the technology to produce variation efficiently. This is the novelty. It is not an artisan making each object individually—it is a machine mass-producing variations.

AP: When printed images became the dominant medium for transmitting architectural knowledge, handmade drawings gradually lost their status as factual documents and became more autonomous artistic expressions. Today, images can be generated, modified, and circulated almost instantaneously. Does the distinction between drawing, model, and image still carry epistemological meaning for architecture?

MC: We just mentioned Walter Benjamin and identical reproduction. But the first person who built a cultural theory of identical copies was five centuries earlier: Leon Battista Alberti. He had no machines. When Alberti came up with his theory of making identical copies, print did not exist—or rather, it existed, but he did not know it. He was writing *De re aedificatoria* around 1452, exactly at the time when Gutenberg was inventing printing with movable type. But Alberti did not know it. He assumed that texts would continue to be reproduced through scribal copying, as they always had been. He knew, as a humanist scholar, that copying introduces errors. Every copyist makes mistakes. That is why Renaissance scholars, when rediscovering classical texts—Vitruvius, Cicero, Quintilian—found multiple versions, all different. This led to the invention of philology: reconstructing the original text by comparing copies. So, Alberti understood that textual transmission is unstable. For this reason, he refused to use images in his treatises. He preferred *verbis solis*—words alone—because he believed that the drift of textual errors

could be controlled more easily than the drift of visual ones. A drawing copied by another artist could deviate significantly from the original. Words, even if corrupted, could be more easily corrected through comparison. Thus, Alberti translated visual ideas into textual descriptions, in order to preserve authorial control. That was the condition of scribal culture. Then Gutenberg's printing changed everything. Within a generation, printing spread across Europe—not only because of accuracy, but because it was cheaper. Identical reproduction became both technically and economically dominant.

Now, Alberti also defines architecture in a very specific way. At the beginning of *De re aedificatoria*, he writes that architecture is not a building, but an idea conceived in the mind, expressed through drawings and models, and then executed without change.

There is:

- first, an idea
- then a drawing (an identical copy of the idea)
- then a building (an identical copy of the drawing)

This only works if identical copies are possible. Alberti's theory depends on reproducibility—even though the technology did not yet exist. That is why he is so important. He anticipates a technological condition that would only emerge later. He never saw his book printed. He died before its publication. But he had heard that in Germany there was a machine capable of producing more copies in one hour than a scriptorium could in a week. He understood that something was changing, even if he did not fully experience it. In that sense, the logic of identical reproduction is not Benjamin's invention—it begins with Alberti.

AP: Recent developments in machine learning, particularly generative models, have reintroduced the notions of style and imitation (*mimesis*) into technological practice. If such systems operate by recombining precedents within datasets, what does this suggest about the role of imitation in artistic creation? And how does this relate to the parametric “space of possibilities,” where potentially infinite variations can be produced and where the idea of “mass individualisation” first emerged?

MC: Mass customisation we have already discussed. But imitation is the core topic here. We think, as modern people, that imitation is a bad

thing—something we should avoid. If a student in an architecture school is told, “you are imitating,” it means failure. It means you will not become a good architect. We have this prejudice: imitation is a crime, something to be hidden, something shameful. But this is a modern idea. In the classical tradition, imitation was the foundation of most art, science, and technology. It was called *mimesis* in Greek, *imitatio* or *emulatio* in Latin. The ancients did not always define these terms precisely; instead, they used stories. For example, the painter Zeuxis. One story: he painted grapes so realistically that birds came and tried to eat them. That is imitation as perfect copying—realism. But there is another story. He was asked to paint the most beautiful woman—an ideal figure, someone like Helen of Troy. He searched for a perfect model but could not find one. So, he selected five different women and combined their features. The final image did not copy any one of them, but incorporated the best of each. People could recognize elements, but could not say exactly which part came from which model. He produced something better than any individual instance of reality.

There are two kinds of imitation, then:

- imitation as copying reality (the grapes)
- imitation as improving upon reality (the ideal figure)

The second is what we may call creative imitation. You do not imitate one model—you imitate many, select, transform, and produce something new: similar to all, identical to none. This is how imitation was understood in the classical tradition and in the Renaissance. This idea was applied not only to images, but also to writing: how to imitate Cicero or Virgil without becoming a mere copyist. The bad imitator is like a mirror or a monkey—someone who reproduces the original without transformation. The good imitator creates something new by selecting and transforming. This model of imitation remained dominant until the Industrial Revolution. With photography, people realized that machines could reproduce reality better than humans. Imitation lost its prestige, and modern art moved away from it. Now, with generative AI, imitation returns. But it does not return as copying—it returns as transformation. Generative AI does what Zeuxis did, but with millions of models instead of five. It processes vast datasets and produces outputs that are derived from them—similar to all, identical to none. This is not copying. It is inspiration, assimilation, transformation. That is why our traditional legal

and conceptual frameworks—copyright, originality—struggle to apply. Copyright is based on identical reproduction. You pay royalties for copying. But there is no “right of inspiration.” If you are inspired by Leonardo, you do not pay royalties. Only if you reproduce his work identically. Generative AI operates in this domain of inspiration, not copying. It works more like the human mind than like a mechanical reproduction system. And this is precisely why we struggle to understand it: for the past two centuries, we have modelled creativity on machines, forgetting that human creativity does not work that way.

Making identical copies is difficult for humans—we are not photocopy machines. But being inspired, transforming what we see, producing something new—that is what we do all the time. That is how the human mind works. If you want identical copies, use a machine. But inspiration and transformation—that is human.

MARCO VANUCCI: Michael Polanyi famously argued that we “know more than we can tell.” Today, AI systems seem to reverse this condition: machines produce results that even their creators cannot fully explain. What does this opacity mean for architectural knowledge?

MC: Yes, this is a very important point. Polanyi’s idea—that we know more than we can tell—refers to tacit knowledge, to forms of understanding that cannot be fully articulated in explicit terms. Now, with AI, we have a different situation. Machines produce results that even their creators cannot fully explain. This is what we call opacity. But this is not entirely unprecedented. In many fields, especially in craft and artistic practice, we already operate with forms of knowledge that are not fully explicit. A skilled artisan may not be able to explain exactly how they achieve a certain result. Opacity is not entirely new. What is new is that it is now embedded in a technical system. With rule-based systems, we could always reconstruct the logic. With machine learning, we cannot. So, we move from a system of explicit knowledge to a system where results emerge from processes that are not fully transparent. This raises important questions for architecture, because architecture has traditionally relied on forms of knowledge that could be communicated, transmitted, and justified. Now we have systems that produce results without fully explainable reasoning. The question becomes: how do we validate, how do we trust, how do we use such knowledge? This is still an open question.

MV: Architecture has historically used computation as a tool for optimisation and control. Yet artists have often embraced technical systems for their unpredictability. Do you think architecture has underestimated the creative potential of computational indeterminacy?

MC: Yes, I think that is true. Architecture has traditionally used computation as a tool for control—for optimisation, for efficiency, for precision. But computational systems can also produce unexpected results. Artists have often explored this dimension—using systems not only to control outcomes, but to generate variation, unpredictability, even error. In architecture, this potential has not always been fully embraced. Partly because architecture is a discipline that must deal with constraints—technical, economic, regulatory. But also because of a cultural preference for control. Now, with generative systems, we are beginning to see a shift. Indeterminacy is no longer simply a limitation; it can be a resource. But again, this requires a change in mindset.

MV: Universities once functioned both as institutions that selected social elites and acted as gatekeepers of knowledge. Today knowledge is widely accessible and higher education has become increasingly democratised. In this context, what role should educational institutions play when professional practice no longer depends on mastering a fixed body of knowledge, but on the ability to think critically and adapt continuously?

MC: Yes, this is a major transformation. Universities were historically institutions that controlled access to knowledge. Knowledge was scarce and education was the way to access it. Today, knowledge is widely available. However, the role of education is changing. It is no longer primarily about transmitting a fixed body of knowledge. It is about developing the ability to think, to interpret, to adapt. In architecture, this is particularly important, because the tools, the technologies, the conditions of practice are constantly changing. Education must focus less on stable content and more on critical thinking. This does not mean that knowledge is no longer important, but that its role is different. The challenge is to redefine what it means to be educated in a context where knowledge is no longer scarce.

MV: Could what Jean Baudrillard described as “copies without originals” help us understand what we are witnessing with generative AI today?

MC: Copies with too many originals, which is the same thing, but originals that are no longer traceable. We can put one million originals in the dataset, but we have no idea what generative AI does to transform them. We call it a black box.

MV: If we look at generative and algorithmic art, particularly in the 1960s, artists often embraced unpredictability as a productive dimension of working with machines. Could this offer a way for architects to reestablish agency today—by engaging with indeterminacy rather than control?

MC: That is the degree of unpredictability. The etymology of cybernetics was originally κυβερνήτης, the pilot of the boat. One could say that the real avatar of cybernetics today is the self-driving car, as Norbert Wiener imagined it in 1948. And what it has to do is not to be rule-based, because you don't know when you're driving if that cat is going to cross the road or not. You must have a way of reacting to what that cat does. You see the cat, but you don't know if it's going to cross one way or another. This is the unpredictability to which the human is capable of giving a response. A traditional rule-based machine cannot react to that. But the principle of cybernetics—feedback—is what today the self-driving car assumes and is capable of doing in the way we do it. They train the self-driving car not with rules but with a dataset of incidents. They have a dataset of one million cars meeting one million cats. Out of this dataset, they extrapolate statistically what is the best thing to do. It is a statistical probability, which no human can calculate. If you are a human driving that car, you can pull from your experience of something similar you have seen. But a dataset with millions of examples of black cats about to cross a road is likely to know more about cat behaviour than we do. So, it would probably avoid more cats than we would.

MV: Therefore, to quote Polanyi again, “we know more than we can tell,” which can be suitably applied to what an architect traditionally goes through in the education process. We tend to know things that we cannot fully explain because there is a certain sensitivity that we develop. The late Yona Friedman argued that architecture is best learned through apprenticeship rather than purely formal education. This perspective aligns with Michael Polanyi's notion that “we know more than we can tell.” In architectural education, much of what is learned cannot be fully articulated, as it involves developing a certain sensitivity through practice.

Therefore, the experiential nature of apprenticeship becomes essential. How does AI interrogate the way we learn?

MC: Anthropologists have a name for that—they call it tacit knowledge. It was thought to be the escape door of the idiots—those who cannot explain what they are doing. I remember so many teachers in design studios who, instead of coming with a theory or rules, would say: I don't have a theory. Just look at me and do what I do.

But this is imitation learning, which is the traditional attitude of an artisan. Think of a bricklayer, or a stonemason building a dry stone wall. There is no handbook that explains the most effective way of doing that, because every stone is different. You cannot learn that from books. You learn by following a master—watching, imitating. The master does not give you a book and say, “read this.” He says, follow me, watch what I do, and one day you will do the same. Imitation learning. Now, oddly, generative AI works that way. If I have a dataset with one million bricklayers laying bricks, the machine will imitate that without knowing any rules. That's the problem: monkey see, monkey do. Monkeys can imitate, but they cannot explain what they are doing. This is tacit knowledge. We are training monkeys. Computers are today's automated monkey. I don't know if it's a good thing.

Perhaps with a good recipe book, I could learn to make good risotto in one week and not in twelve years. But it's all about learning by rules or learning by observation. We can learn a lot of things without knowing any rules. When we go to school at the age of six, we already know how to speak, even though we cannot yet read. By simply imitating the sounds we hear—our parents—we learn to communicate. We have an extraordinary capacity to imitate, which is specific to primates—monkeys, apes, and us. Dogs cannot imitate; cats cannot imitate. They learn by trial and error. So having a machine that can now imitate in this way is somewhat disconcerting.

MV: In the past, you would go to university because there was a library. Now knowledge is everywhere. Institutions are no longer selecting the ruling class. There is democratization of knowledge and education. What should we do?

MC: What you describe is the modernist dream—a social democratic dream where universities are responsible for transmitting and protecting

knowledge. Does it still work that way? Nobody gives a fig about knowledge today. Universities are universally despised as places where people replicate useless knowledge. We live in a world where violence and action are more important than competence and expertise. There is a hypothetical which I always use in this case. Imagine living in an Alpine valley. At some point you realize that your pastures do not grow enough wheat to feed your population because of climate change, or there is no rain anymore, or the wheat is not strong. People are starving. There used to be food and now there isn't. What do you do? There are two paths. Number one is science: you become an engineer. You improve the yield of the pastures and the wheat, the quality of the grains and the tools you are using in agriculture. With technology, you improve the performance of the land you live on. You feed your people again with better technology. Number two: you cross the watershed, you go to the next valley, you kill everyone and steal their wheat. The choice is between war or science. During the second half of the twentieth century, we thought that science was the good solution. And now again it's war, as we see. It's easier to go and steal. Because if you're an engineer, you don't need war. You don't need to steal your neighbour's wheat if you can get better wheat from your pastures. Perhaps that's one thing universities can still do: train our future engineers, hoping we shall still need them.

Interview conducted by Andreja Prokopijević, Željko Radinković, and Marco Vanucci.